

Removal of Zn^{2+} in aqueous solution by Linde F (K) zeolite prepared from recycled fly ash

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Abstract : Linde F (K) zeolite is used for removing Zn^{II} from aqueous solution. The zeolite is synthesized between fly ash and 8 M KOH solution by hydrothermal process (liquid/solid = 5 and 95 °C). The XRD and SEM-EDS are used to study zeolite characteristics. The studying experiment parameters are adsorption temperature, zeolite dosage and solution pH. The results show that Zn^{II} removal could be improved by increasing temperature. The optimal solution pH and most efficient zeolite dosage is 7 and 5 g/L respectively. Pseudo-second order model and Langmuir isotherm shows better calculation results for the adsorption of Zn^{II} on Linde F (K). The endothermic adsorption process is spontaneous and the adsorption becomes more spontaneous with temperature increasing.

Keywords : Zn, adsorption, Linde F(K), zeolite, fly ash.

Introduction

In our world, heavy metal pollution has become a severe public health problem¹⁻³. The heavy metal in aqueous solution could join the food chain and then has the toxic effects on the environment and human beings⁴. So, removal of heavy metals from wastewater prior to be discharged to natural water is one of important environment tasks all over the world.

As we know, Zn^{II} is an essential trace element and act as a micronutrient for human being. But, excessive intake Zn^{II} would lead to many serious healthy problems including irritability, muscular stiffness, loss of appetite, nausea⁵. After bioaccumulation, Zn^{II} would even reach flora and fauna which lead to ecological problems. Everyday, plenty of Zn^{II} pollution is produced from metal plating facilities, battery manufacturing processes, production of paints, pigments insecticides, cosmetics, etc.⁵. Considering its toxic effect, Zn^{II} has to be removed before wastewater discharged to natural water.

Now, conventional Zn^{II} removal technologies are

chemical precipitation, ion exchange, membrane filtration, electrolytic methods, solvent extraction and adsorption⁶⁻¹¹. Considering the efficiency and feasibility of industrial application, many researchers suggested that adsorption is most efficient technology, especially for the effluent whose Zn^{II} concentration is lower than 100 mg/L^{12,13}. But, at present, the high cost adsorbent (such as active carbon) has limited the large scale industry application of adsorption technology. So, looking for suitable and relatively cheap adsorbent has attracted extensive research concerning. Among low-cost Zn^{II} adsorbents, fly ash based zeolite has been considered as a most competitive one. Fly ash is a solid waste coming from power plant. Using this recycle industry solid waste as raw material could decrease the cost of adsorbent. Even more important is that the Zn^{II} adsorption capability of fly ash based zeolite has been proved by many researchers. A synthetic zeolite produced from fly ash was applied for Zn, Cu, Mn and Pb adsorption¹⁴. Wang suggested that the pure-form zeolites (A and X) synthesized from fly ash

were applied for Zn and Cu adsorption¹⁵. Hui utilized fly ash as raw materials to synthesis zeolite 4A and it showed remarkable for mixed heavy metal ions¹⁶. Rios used synthetic zeolite prepared by fly ash to remove heavy metals from acid mine drainage¹⁷.

Linde F (K) zeolite is a product gained from hydrothermal reaction between fly ash and high concentration KOH solution. Miyaji has successfully used fly ash to synthesize it on 2009 and then in his published paper, he implied its potential for adsorption¹⁸. Unfortunately, so far, no further experiment results about its adsorption capability have been reported. The main objective of this paper is to evaluate the feasibility of removing Zn^{II} from aqueous solutions using Linde F (K) zeolite prepared by fly ash. The influence of several important parameters including solution pH, zeolite dosage, contact time and adsorption temperature are investigated. Adsorption kinetics, isotherm and thermodynamic are also discussed.

Results and discussion

Characteristics of adsorbents :

Fig. 1 shows the XRD patterns and SEM images of synthesis zeolite. As Fig. 1, it could be found that new crystalline peaks belong to Linde type F (K) zeolite (2θ : 32.14°, 30.34°, 29.01°, etc., PDF No. 38-0216) appears on the XRD pattern besides the peak of quartz (2θ : 50.26°, 26.74°, 20.96°, etc.) and mullite (2θ : 26.20°, 25.80°, 16.5° etc.) which comes from original fly ash. On the basis of SEM image, the new crystalline zeolite has hexahedron microstructure. With the help of EDS, we know that the micro-composition of crystalline (atomic %) are

Fig. 1. XRD and SEM results of Linde F (K) zeolite.

about 15.33% K, 15.68% Si and 15.53% Al and 53.46% O, which is generally consistent with the chemical formula of Linde F (K), $(KAlSiO_4 \cdot xH_2O)$.

Adsorption temperature and contact time :

Fig. 2 shows how adsorption temperature and contact time affect the adsorption efficiency. As shown in Fig. 2, temperature has an important influence on adsorption efficiency. Under 20 °C, the Zn^{II} removal only could reach about 79.8% after 5 h while under 60 °C, the Zn^{II} removal achieve about 83.12% after only 1 h. In addition, adsorption temperature not only influenced the adsorption rate but in turn can affect the equilibrium contact time. The equilibrium contact time decreases from about 6 h to 2 h with adsorption temperature increases from 40 to 60 °C. Wang ascribed temperature act on adsorption efficiency as follow : (a) more heat energy is supplied to dehydration of metal ions which results to metals ions enter the pores of zeolite freely, (b) the viscosity of solution could decrease after temperature increasing, which promote the metal ions enter into interior surface of zeolite¹⁵.

Fig. 2. Effect of contact time and adsorption temperature on removal efficient of Zn^{II}.

Solution pH :

The solution pH plays an important role in the adsorption process of Zn^{II} on zeolite. The variation of adsorption of Zn^{II} on zeolite over pH from 3 to 9 is showed in Fig. 3. As Fig. 3, the removal efficiency of Zn^{II} increases with the solution pH and could reach about 100% when solution pH is higher than 7. As we know, the results should be attributed to 2 reasons. Firstly, lower

Fig. 3. Effect of pH on removal efficient of Zn^{II}.

pH would decrease the removal efficiency because H_3O^+ ion is adsorption competitor of Zn. Secondly, the higher solution pH would lead to the precipitation of Zn and causes the removal efficiency higher. In order to study the true adsorption control process of Zn on zeolite, the optimal solution pH of our experiment is chosen as 7.

Zeolite dosage :

Fig. 4 shows how zeolite dosage affects the adsorption efficiency. As Fig. 4, an increasing of zeolite dosage favors Zn^{II} removal. A significant enhancement in the Zn^{II} removal (about 20.03% to nearly 100%) could be found when zeolite dosage ranges from 0.5 to 12 g/L. It should be resulted from more adsorption sites which are supplied from higher zeolite dosage. On the other hand, Fig. 4 also tells us that the saturated adsorption amount undergoes a continuous decrease from 40.06 mg/g to 8.33 mg/g with zeolite dosage increasing. This implies that zeolite dosage should be chosen in a reasonable range.

Fig. 4. Effect of zeolite dosage on removal efficient and saturated adsorption amount of Zn^{II}.

Considering above results, the optimal zeolite dosage is chosen as 5 g/L.

Adsorption kinetics :

The Lagergren pseudo-first order model and Blanchard pseudo-second order model are used to analyze adsorption kinetics. The equations of two models are showed below¹⁹⁻²¹ :

The Lagergren pseudo-first order model

$$\ln(q_e - q) = \ln q_e - k_1 t \tag{1}$$

where q_e is equilibrium adsorption amount of Zn on zeolite (mg/g), q is adsorption amount of Zn^{II} on zeolite at time t (mg/g), k_1 is rate constant of first order model and t is contact time.

The Blanchard pseudo-second order model

$$\frac{t}{q} = \frac{1}{kq_e^2} + \frac{t}{q_e} \tag{2}$$

where k_2 is rate constant of second order model.

The two models are used to plot the data in Fig. 2 and the results are showed in Fig. 5, Fig. 6 and Table 1. According to references, R^2 value (correlation coefficient)

Fig. 5. Pseudo-first order kinetics plot for adsorption of Zn^{II}.

of plot and root mean square error (RMSE) are always used to evaluate the rationality of the model²². The RMSE are defined as follow :

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (q_{exp} - q_{cal})^2}{N}} \tag{3}$$

where q_{exp} and q_{cal} is equilibrium adsorption amount of Zn^{II} on zeolite (mg/g) gained from experiments and model calculation.

Fig. 6. Pseudo-second order kinetics plot for adsorption of Zn^{II} .

Table 1. Pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order rate constants calculated from experiment data

Temp. (°C)	Pseudo-first order			Pseudo-second order		
	k_1 (h)	q_{cal} (mg/g)	R^2	k_2 (g/mg·h)	q_{cal} (mg/g)	R^2
20	0.2188	12.11	0.9975	0.05274	18.59	0.9919
40	0.3307	11.37	0.9623	0.06831	20.16	0.9872
60	0.9957	8.68	0.9681	0.2490	20.75	0.9997
q_{exp} (mg/g)	RMSE					
20	7.89			1.41		
	8.63			0.16		
	11.32			0.75		

As shown in Table 1, it is obviously found that pseudo-second order model could give higher R^2 value (0.9872–0.9997) than first order model (0.9681–0.9975). On the other hand, the RMSE (0.75–1.41) of pseudo-second order model is much lower than first order model (7.89–11.32). Both of these indicate that pseudo-second order model is more applicable to the adsorption kinetics of Zn^{II} on Linde F (K).

Adsorption isotherm and thermodynamic :

For adsorption isotherm, Freundlich isotherm and Langmuir isotherm are usually applied. The equations are as follow^{23–25} :

Langmuir isotherm :

$$\frac{C_e}{q_e} = \frac{1}{k_L q_m} + \frac{C_e}{q_m} \tag{4}$$

where q_e and C_e are the amount adsorbed (mg/g) and the adsorbate concentration on solution (mg/L), both at equilibrium; k_L (L/mg) is the Langmuir constant related to the energy of adsorption; and q_m (mg/g) is the maximum adsorption capacity.

Freundlich isotherm :

$$\ln q_e = \ln k_F + (1/n) \ln C_e \tag{5}$$

where k_F and n are constants for the Freundlich isotherm, they are indicative of the adsorption capacity (mg/g) and adsorption intensity.

Table 2 shows calculation results of Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm. It could be seen that Langmuir isotherm gives better calculation results. The R^2 of Langmuir isotherm (0.9653–0.9941) is much higher than the value of Freundlich isotherm (0.8339–0.9134). It tells us that the Zn^{II} adsorption on Linde F (K) zeolite is a monolayer adsorption procedure.

Table 2. Adsorption isotherms constants calculated from experiment data

Temp. (K)	Langmuir			Freundlich		
	q_m (mg/g)	k_L (L/mg)	R^2	k_f	n	R^2
293	41.49	0.0662	0.9744	10.36	3.64	0.9134
313	44.25	0.0912	0.9653	13.76	5.03	0.8339
333	45.04	0.128	0.9941	16.16	4.63	0.9007

Table 3 shows Langmuir maximum adsorption capacity (q_m) of other adsorbents. Compared with these

Table 3. Langmuir maximum adsorption capacity (q_m) of different adsorbents

Adsorbent	q_m (mg/g)
Linde F (K) zeolite	45.04
Vermicompost ²⁶	20.48
Crosslinked starch phosphates ²⁷	76.72
Calcinated Chinese loess ²⁸	62.344
Humic acid ²⁹	6.12
Clarified sludge ³⁰	15.53
Rice husk ash ³⁰	14.30
Activated alumina ³⁰	13.69
Neem bark ³⁰	13.29
Fly ash ³¹	0.644

adsorbents, the q_m of Linde F (K) zeolite shows medium-high value. Considering that the fly ash is a solid waste, this q_m value implies the potential of Linde F (K) zeolite to be one of competitive Zn adsorbent and broad application prospect.

Because the Langmuir isotherm is more suitable for the fitting of adsorption data, the equilibrium constant of Langmuir isotherm (k_L) are used for thermodynamic study. The equations are as follow³¹⁻³⁴ and the results are showed in Table 4.

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln k_L \quad (6)$$

$$\ln k_L = -\frac{\Delta H}{RT} + \frac{\Delta S}{R} \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta G = \Delta H - T\Delta S \quad (8)$$

where k_L is the Langmuir constant (L/g). ΔG , ΔH and ΔS are Gibbs free energy, enthalpy and entropy, respectively (kJ/mol). R is the gas constant, and T is the absolute temperature.

Table 4. Adsorption thermodynamic constants calculated from experiment data

Temp. (K)	ΔG (kJ/mol)	ΔH (kJ/mol)	ΔS (kJ/mol K)
293.15	-10.213		
313.15	-11.744	13.398	0.0804
333.15	-13.433		

For the adsorption of Zn on Linde F (K) zeolite, the values of ΔG varied between -10.213 and -13.433 kJ/mol. The negative values of ΔG tell us that the adsorption process is spontaneous under temperature from 20-60 °C and the adsorption become more spontaneous at higher temperatures. Then the ΔH and ΔS showing positive value tells us that the adsorption is endothermic and that the disorder in the system has increased.

Experimental

Chemicals :

The aqueous solution of Zn^{II} is prepared through dissolving $Zn(NO_3)_2$ in DI water and the concentration is 100 mg/L. Alkaline solution used for zeolite synthesis is prepared through dissolving KOH in DI water. The solutions used for adjusting adsorption pH are prepared through dissolving NaOH and HCl in DI water. All chemicals used in our experiment are analytical reagent and bought

from China National Pharmaceutical Group Corporation.

Zeolite synthesis and character :

The Linde F (K) zeolite is synthesized through fly ash reacted with KOH solution. The original fly ash is gained from Taicang Harbour Golden Concord Electric-Power Generation Co. Ltd. (Taicang, Jiangsu Province). The main chemical composition are SiO_2 (56.71%), Al_2O_3 (28.9%), CaO (2.34%), Fe_2O_3 (4.02%), Na_2O (0.46%), MgO (0.04%), K_2O (1.32%) and TiO_2 (1.07%). The zeolite synthesis procedures are as follow (Fig. 7) : Firstly, in order to get rid of un-burned carbon and other impurities, the original fly ash is mixed with DI water (liquid/solid = 5, 200 rpm and room temperature) and then the mixture is left to stand. After the mixture liquid is separated into solid and liquid, the supernatant solution is abandoned and the deposit sediment is filtered with 0.45 μm membrane. The solid is dry to constant weight under 150 °C. Secondly the dry fly ash is mixed with 8 M KOH solution for 5 h (liquid/solid = 5, 200 rpm and 95 °C). After reaction, the mixture is also filtered with 0.45 μm membrane. To reduce the cost of zeolite synthesis, the alkaline solution obtained from early filters (whose pH is

Fig. 7. The procedure of zeolite synthesis.

much higher than 14) is recycled for alkaline treatment of fly ash (total about 50 times). For solid reaction products, huge amount of DI water is used to wash them to clean the residue alkali until the pH of filtrate reach about 7. Finally, the filter solid is also dry to constant weight under 150 °C. The zeolite is character by XRD and SEM-EDS. The X-ray diffraction patterns for the powder samples are taken on a Shimadzu XD-3A diffractometer, using Cu-K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.54056 \text{ \AA}$). The morphologies of the composites are observed on an X-650 scanning electron microscope.

Adsorption experiments :

The adsorption experiments are conducted as typical batch studies. The zeolite is mixed with 10 ml Zn^{II} solution in 20 ml Teflon bottles. The bottles with mixtures are fixed in a water bath shaking box and shaken at 200 rpm. After adsorption, the mixtures are filtered with 0.45 μm membrane and then the concentration of Zn^{II} in solution is measured by AA240FS atomic adsorption spectrophotometry.

According to the unit procedure, the effect of solution pH on adsorption is conducted as 3–10 of pH, 4 h contact time, 5 g zeolite and 40 °C. The pH of solution is adjusted by 0.01 mol/L NaOH and 0.01 mol/L HCl solution. The pH of solution is determined by a Q/GHSC 1544-2009 pH meter.

The effect of zeolite dosage on adsorption is carried out as 5 to 8 g/L zeolite, 7 of pH, 4 h contact time and 40 °C. The effect of contact time and temperature on adsorption is run as 0.5 to 6 h contact time, 20 to 60 °C, 7 of pH and 5 g/L zeolite.

Conclusions

The Linde F (K) zeolite could be synthesized from fly ash by hydrothermal process (liquid/solid = 5 and 95 °C). The adsorption rate could be accelerated by higher solution temperature. The efficient solution pH and zeolite dosage is 7 and 5 g/L respectively. For adsorption kinetics, pseudo-second order model shows better calculation results, and for adsorption isotherm, Langmuir isotherm are more applicable to explain this monolayer adsorption procedure of Zn^{II} on Linde F (K) zeolite. The endothermic adsorption process is spontaneous and become more spontaneous at higher temperatures.

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